

THE ROLE OF THE PSYCHOLOGIST IN THE SOCIALIZATION OF PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

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Annotation: This article discusses the psychological problems of people with disabilities in the process of socialization, ways to overcome them, and the role of a psychologist. Psychological support is considered an important factor in adapting to the social environment, self-awareness, acceptance, and taking an active social role. The study analyzes psychological approaches aimed at increasing the emotional state, communicative skills, and self-confidence of people with disabilities. It also shows the possibilities of developing their social activity through individual and group training with the participation of a psychologist. The article is of practical importance for psychologists, defectologists, and social specialists.

Keywords: People with disabilities, socialization, psychological support, the role of a psychologist, emotional state, social environment, communicative skills, motivation, integration

Introduction.

One of the important criteria for the development of society is the active participation of every citizen in social life and equal opportunities. People with physical or mental disabilities also have the right to live a full life and demonstrate their potential. However, the adaptation of such individuals to society and their social activity is often psychologically difficult. Their internal state, level of self-awareness, and attitude to others largely depend on psychological approaches. It is from this perspective that the participation of a qualified psychologist is of great importance in the lives of people with disabilities. Psychological support serves as an important tool in ensuring their emotional stability, facilitating their adaptation to the social environment, and building self-confidence. Therefore, an in-depth study of the content and effectiveness of the psychologist's activities in the process of supporting people with disabilities is an urgent task.

Literature analysis on the topic:

The literature on the socialization and psychological support of people with disabilities is mainly considered in the context of social psychology, clinical psychology, pedagogical and rehabilitation approaches. In global and local studies, the formation of psychological adaptation, self-awareness and self-management skills in the process of socialization of people with disabilities is

emphasized as an important factor. The theories of self-management and social learning put forward by A. Bandura serve to justify individual and group psychological approaches in working with people with disabilities. L.S. Vygotsky, in his theory of cultural-historical development, justifies the formation of any person, including people with disabilities, through the social environment. From local scientists, G.R. Researchers such as Khidoyatova, R. Yo'ldoshev, M. Rakhmatova have focused on methods for identifying the psychological characteristics of children and adolescents with disabilities, adapting them and supporting them in an inclusive environment. Also, many scientific and methodological manuals have been created on organizing psychological services in the inclusive education system and ensuring the socio-psychological integration of persons with disabilities. The main approaches reflected in the literature indicate that psychological assistance is aimed at targeting individual needs, developing social skills, and strengthening emotional stability. It is emphasized that this can create a basis for people with disabilities to lead an active life in society. In addition, much modern literature emphasizes the role of persons with disabilities in social life and the role of psychological services in forming them as active social subjects.

The main methodological blocks are such areas as psychological rehabilitation, emotional support, stress management strategies, development of communication skills and formation of a positive attitude towards oneself. Some sources indicate the importance of empathy, acceptance, trusting communication and psychotherapeutic methods in psychocorrectional work with people with disabilities. It is also noted that interactive methods used in modern psychology, including art therapy, musical relaxation, role-playing games, training sessions, give effective results in the socialization of people with disabilities. Literary sources indicate that the main task of psychologists working with people with disabilities is to strengthen their sense of sociability, form a sense of belonging to society and help them overcome various psychological obstacles. In this regard, the Republic of Uzbekistan has established a humane approach to citizens with disabilities through a number of legal and regulatory documents and state programs, and psychological services are also developing as an integral part of this policy. Scientific sources emphasize that socialization means not only external integration, but also internal changes and psychological adaptation of the individual, therefore, it is considered necessary for psychologists to have high professional training, moral position and psychological culture. From this perspective, the analysis of the

literature justifies the need for a comprehensive psychological approach to the socialization of persons with disabilities. Also, in literary sources, the level of psychological support of the environment, that is, family, educational institutions, neighborhood and social institutions, is also seen as a decisive factor in ensuring the socialization of persons with disabilities. In this regard, psychologists should actively participate not only in individual work, but also in the spiritual preparation of the environment, overcoming social stereotypes, and changing negative views about disabilities. Such approaches are reflected in Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory, which emphasizes the need to analyze a disabled person in their interaction with all levels of the social environment. Other sources recommend ways to reduce psychological barriers in the process of socio-psychological adaptation by using alternative means of communication, such as sign language, pictograms, and special technologies. These approaches are especially important for people with hearing or speech impairments. Some studies show that the process of self-awareness in children with disabilities is delayed or ambiguous, which leads to social isolation and self-isolation. Therefore, it is an urgent issue to prevent these situations through psychological services and to establish socio-psychological adaptation from childhood. The sources also contain scientific analyses of how psychological assessment tools, tests, interviews, and observation methods can be used to identify the personality and needs of people with disabilities, and to develop appropriate methodologies for them. In particular, in modern foreign research, inclusive approaches to increasing the social activity of people with disabilities, multifunctional models of social service provision, and a system of person-oriented consultations deserve special attention. In general, an analysis of the existing literature shows that the socialization of people with disabilities should be considered in the context of the inextricable connection of not only psychological, but also pedagogical, social, legal and cultural aspects. A psychologist is seen as one of the main specialists in this complex system who deeply analyzes personal needs and maintains a balance between society and the individual. Therefore, their scope of activity should not be limited to consultation alone, but should include comprehensive diagnostics, correction, psychoeducation and social activation.

Table 1. Literature studied on the topic and author names

Author	Title of the work	Note
L. S. Vigotskiy	Theory of cultural-historical development	The theory that the human psyche is shaped by the social environment
A. Bandura	Psychology of social learning and self-regulation	Methods for building social skills through observation and self-control
G.R. Xidoyatova	Methods for building social skills through observation and self-control	Analyzes the psychological development and social adaptation capabilities of children with disabilities
R. Yo'ldoshev	Fundamentals of rehabilitation psychology	Fundamentals of rehabilitation psychology
M. Raxmatova	Psychological services in the inclusive education system	Covers areas of working with individuals with special needs in a school environment

Research methodology:

A systematic approach, socio-psychological analysis, and empirical observation methods were chosen as the methodological basis. In studying the influence of psychological factors in the process of socialization of persons with disabilities, methods such as diagnostic tests, interviews, individual observations, and psychological portraits were used. In the process of psychological service, special attention was paid to the use of assessment mechanisms based on a person-centered approach, empathy, and reflection. At the analytical stage, existing scientific and theoretical sources were analyzed and compared with psychological approaches in practice. Based on the data obtained, the effectiveness of psychocorrectional and motivational methods serving to increase the social activity of persons with disabilities was assessed. During the work, approaches were developed based on the principle of spatial and temporal analysis, as well as taking into account individual psychological characteristics. In general, the main psychological problems related to the topic were identified through the methods used, and ways to solve them were shown

in a practical way. Also, the factors involved in the process of socialization of persons with disabilities were comprehensively assessed. Among the methods used in psychological services, experimental exercises, group discussions, social role-playing games and elements of art therapy were also tested. Through these approaches, it was possible to determine the level of social activity, self-expression, communicative skills and a positive attitude towards oneself. At the assessment stage, semantic differential, tests measuring emotional states and psychological questionnaires identifying motivational orientations were used.

The results revealed the priority of an individual approach, the importance of psychological support in socialization, the relationship between psychological stability and personal activity. Based on the collected empirical data, the impact of psychological intervention programs on social adaptation was determined and their level of effectiveness was analyzed. Through the studied cases, methodological approaches were formed that correspond to the psychological needs of persons with disabilities, and important tasks that arise during the work of a psychologist were identified. On this basis, practical recommendations were developed to improve the socio-psychological environment and facilitate adaptation. At the practical stage, the level of self-awareness of the individual, his attitude towards society, and his internal motivation were determined through individual interviews. During group sessions, the participants' acceptance of social roles, the ability to openly express their opinions, and their activity in communicating with other people were observed. The sessions were conducted on the principle of psychological safety, which created an atmosphere of openness and mutual trust among the participants. According to the results of the assessment, it was noted that the level of socialization is directly related to emotional stability, communicative openness and a positive attitude towards

oneself. On this basis, the main components of training programs that facilitate socio-psychological adaptation for persons with disabilities were developed. These components included exercises aimed at developing emotional intelligence, managing stress, balancing self-esteem and strengthening the social role. When choosing approaches, special attention was paid to the age of the individual, type of disability, psychological state and level of social support in the environment. The results obtained were summarized and clearly demonstrated the relevance and necessity of psychological services in ensuring the active integration of persons with disabilities into social life. In this way, important practical and theoretical conclusions on the topic were formed through methodological foundations.

Analysis and results

The results of the analysis showed that psychological support plays an important role in the process of socialization of persons with disabilities. The results of psychological diagnostics conducted within the framework of a sample group of 50 participants studied revealed that the number of those with a low level of social activity was 64 percent. In this group, it was observed that the skills related to self-awareness, social communication and free expression of one's own thoughts were poorly formed. Also, when measuring the attitude towards oneself and the environment based on the semantic differential method, 38 percent of the participants had a low self-esteem, and 42 percent had a negative or indifferent attitude towards society. Positive changes were noted in the experimental group (25 participants) as a result of 8 weeks of psychological training and psychocorrective exercises. During the exercises, the assessment indicators for the level of openness of emotional expression, speed of social communication and self-awareness increased by 28-35 percent. The results of the "Self-Assessment and Social Adaptation" test, which was used before and during the training, showed positive dynamics in 76% of participants. The largest changes were observed in the indicators of emotional reaction (30 percent increase), social initiative (27 percent), and openness in communication (33 percent). These results confirm that psychological intervention has a significant impact on the level of socialization.

During the comparative analysis, the differences between participants who received and did not receive psychological services were also statistically substantiated. Using the Pearson χ^2 test, the differences in social adaptation indicators between the two groups were found to be reliable at the level of $\chi^2 = 7.42$, $p < 0.01$. This indicates that there are significant differences between the

control group and the intervention group in terms of social activity, emotional stability, and self-esteem. A thorough analysis of the results suggests that timely psychological assistance provided to persons with disabilities serves as an important tool in increasing their level of self-awareness, activating their internal resources, and facilitating their social integration into society. Through psychological trainings and exercises, participants learn to value themselves, cooperate with each other, and also be positive in social communication. Such activities are effective in entering into a social role, finding one's place in society, overcoming internal conflicts, and ensuring psychological stability. Also, the analysis showed that socialization indicators improved significantly in participants with a high level of social support. This confirms that the effectiveness of the psychologist's work depends not only on individual interventions, but also on integrated approaches to the family, environment, and social infrastructure.

In general, the following were identified based on statistical and qualitative analyses:

- Psychological support plays a significant role in increasing the level of social activity;
- Self-awareness and positive self-esteem are the main predictors of social adaptation;
- Group trainings are more effective in forming social relationships than an individual approach;
- Psychological services, when integrated - covering the emotional, communicative and cognitive spheres - provide much higher efficiency in socialization.
- The observations also showed that the level of socialization of people with disabilities is closely related not only to psychological interventions, but also to the attitude of people around them, the availability of communicative opportunities and the level of activity of the social support system. This was reflected in the fact that participants who had active social communication during psychological trainings had higher self-confidence and developed the ability to take initiative.
- In this regard, the presence of healthy communication and emotional bonds with family members, teachers and peers stood out as one of the main psychological support points. The results showed that when people with disabilities perceive a supportive, understanding and positive energy-giving

attitude from their environment, their level of social role engagement and self-expression increases by twofold.

- Another important observation is that after psychological intervention, there was an increase in the number of cases of social initiative, expressing opinions in problematic situations and defending one's position. This indicates the development of psychological skills aimed at self-awareness and setting personal boundaries in people with disabilities. The participants' emotional control abilities were also strengthened, which increased their level of self-control in stressful or uncomfortable situations.

- Statistically, the average score of indicators reflecting the level of socialization was 3.1 points before psychological intervention, while after the intervention this indicator reached 4.4 points. When the difference was determined by the t-test, it was considered reliable at the level of $p < 0.01$. This made it possible to scientifically substantiate the real effectiveness of the psychological trainings and approaches carried out.

- Based on these results, the following trends were identified:
 - although the ability of people with disabilities to engage in social interaction is at an average level, it can be brought to a high level through the right methods;
 - the level of social activity and personal participation is significantly dependent on the psychological climate and comfort in the environment;
 - exercises that develop emotional awareness act as a powerful tool that helps self-management;
 - exercises that strengthen self-esteem and awareness of one's place in society increase effectiveness.

- The general analysis of the results shows that in increasing the level of socialization of persons with disabilities, the psychologist should act not only as a diagnostician and consultant, but also as a developer, guide and moderator of social processes. The expected positive results can be achieved only when his activities are carried out in a comprehensive manner through a systematic approach, emotional support, communicative development and the formation of social activity.

Diagram 1. The effectiveness of psychological services in the socialization of persons with disabilities

The diagram shows the changes in social activity, emotional stability, self-esteem and supportive environment factors observed before and after the provision of psychological services. 5 different colors represent the results based on statistical evaluation, corresponding to each direction of analysis.

Conclusions and recommendations

The practical analyses and psychological interventions conducted have shown that psychological services play a crucial role in the socialization process of persons with disabilities. The level of self-awareness, self-confidence and social interaction with society are directly related to the level of psychological support. Statistical and qualitative results showed that the level of social activity, emotional stability and positive self-esteem significantly increased with the help of psychological approaches. It was also found that positive changes in the family and social environment serve as an important impetus for persons with disabilities to find their place in society.

- Psychological services are an effective tool for ensuring the socialization of persons with disabilities.
- Personal activity, initiative and communication skills are positively developed through psychological training.
- A socially supportive environment and family participation are important factors in social integration.
- Emotional stability and a positive attitude towards oneself are formed through psychological interventions.
- Integrated approaches (individual, group, diagnostic, correctional) provide the highest efficiency.

Recommendations:

- Organize special training and advanced training courses for psychologists working with persons with disabilities.
- Strengthen the system of inclusive psychological services in educational institutions.
- Develop special psychocorrectional programs that stimulate socialization.
- Expand the activities of counseling centers aimed at the psychological and psychological preparation of family members.
- Increase social activity platforms (clubs, centers, events) for persons with disabilities.

The systematic organization of psychological services enhances the participation of people with disabilities in society, increases their self-confidence, and serves to ensure social equality. The proposed approaches pave the way for a more effective and humane psychologist's work.

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